

BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF GLASS FIBRE REINFORCED
PLASTICS SIMPLY-SUPPORTED BEAM HIGHWAY BRIDGE

Ma Xi-Peng
Research Institute of Highway
The Ministry of Communication
Beijing, China

Glass fibre reinforced plastics (GRP) has many distinguishing characteristics, such as lightweight, high strength, easily being shaped, capability of being designed good failure resistance capability, good impact ductility, corrosion proof and etc. So we introduced the GRP material to highway bridge construction and built the first GRP highway bridge in Mi Yun, Beijing in Oct, 1982. After a trial service of 6 years, the structure working condition of this bridge is very good.

Mi Yun GRP highway bridge is a singlespan, simply-supported beam bridge of two traffic lanes with a span length of 20.7 meters and deck width of 11.38 meters. There are 6 GRP honeycomb box beams. Each GRP box beam weighs 6 ton. The weight of whole bridge including is only 1/5 of that of reinforced concrete bridge of same scale.

The design load standards of this GRP highway bridge are:
calculating load: Automobile 15 class.
checking load: Trail 80 class.

Since the completion, the GRP pioneer highway bridge has been Statically and dynamically loading tested to the safety factor of design code requirements.

The practice of the GRP highway bridge proves:

- It is feasible to build GRP highway bridge from technical point of view.
- GRP bridge is intensely competitive economically.

The main advantages of GRP bridge are:

- The weight of bridge can be decreased to a great extent enabling longer span of bridge to be constructed.
- It can be shaped easily and constructed quickly, so the time of construction is short and no major equipment is needed for installation.
- GRP structure is light in weight, aseismic and corrosion-proofed, so it is suitable to region of frequently-occurring and high intensity earthquakes, strongly corrosive environment and soft soil.